

The role of pharmacists in managing mental health disorders: a review

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Abstract

Pharmacists are participants in the treatment and management of mental disorders as integral members of multidisciplinary healthcare teams. Their roles extend beyond dispensing medications to providing counseling, promoting adherence, managing drug interactions, assessing treatment outcomes, and supporting symptom management—all while ensuring empathy and confidentiality. They face challenges such as nonadherence, communication barriers, and public stigma. Pharmacists manage complex drug interactions, particularly those between psychiatric medications and nutritional supplements. In hospitals, clinical pharmacists optimize therapy, monitor treatment effectiveness, and train staff in mental health pharmacotherapy. This article emphasizes the need for specialized training for pharmacists to enhance their mental health care competencies. Countries such as the USA, UK, and Australia have successfully implemented such programs, while Bulgaria is integrating mental health care into pharmaceutical practice, expanding the responsibilities of pharmacists and raising public awareness. These achievements highlight the essential contribution of pharmacists to improving mental health outcomes and addressing related challenges.

Keywords

depression, interdisciplinary collaboration, patient adherence, pharmaceutical counseling, psychotropic drug interactions, substance use disorders

Introduction

Pharmacists are an integral part of the treatment of patients with mental disorders, with responsibilities extending beyond the dispensing of medications. The classification of mental disorders includes a wide range of conditions that influence mood, cognition, behavior, and perception. This category comprises affective disorders, anxiety disorders, psychotic disorders, eating disorders, obsessive-compulsive disorders, cognitive disorders, as well as substance use disorders and

disorders related to stress and trauma. Pharmacists play a crucial role in optimizing pharmacotherapy for patients, ensuring the safe and effective administration of medications for mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, and schizophrenia (Chen 2008; Rubio-Valera et al. 2014; Panesar 2016; Karolewicz et al. 2020). They conduct medication reviews to identify and address medication-related issues, manage polypharmacy, and monitor adverse drug reactions (Tai et al. 2014; Soubolsky and Halpape 2022; Khartabil et al. 2024).

Pharmacists are uniquely positioned to act as the first point of contact for patients in crisis, especially when access to psychiatric services is limited. When identifying worrying indicators, they should provide emergency care guidelines, refer the patient to a doctor, or activate appropriate support networks (Rubio-Valera et al. 2014). Training in areas such as psychological first aid (PFA), de-escalation techniques, and ethics is critical for dealing with such situations.

The necessity for motivation and psychological support is paramount in enhancing therapy adherence. Pharmacists employ strategies such as motivational interviewing, which requires specialized training. This approach enables pharmacists to build rapport and empower patients to make informed decisions regarding their treatment. Confidentiality and ethical considerations are of utmost importance, particularly in the context of mental health disorders. Patients often exhibit heightened sensitivity toward their personal information and health status. Therefore, pharmacists must ensure that discussions are held in environments that prioritize discretion and uphold the patient's right to privacy. Stigma and lack of trust toward healthcare professionals, which can manifest as aggression or hostility, are significant barriers for patients with mental health conditions (Rickles et al. 2010). Such individuals frequently encounter stigma and discrimination, resulting in feelings of distrust and shame during interactions with pharmacists. This environment may inhibit their willingness to disclose pertinent information about their health or adhere to treatment protocols.

It is essential that pharmacists are skilled in identifying early signs of mental health deterioration, including symptoms such as social withdrawal, confusion, mood swings, or expressions of hopelessness. This requires specialized knowledge in the field of mental health, as well as developed communication skills to allow for adequate assessment of the condition and the need for medical intervention (O'Reilly et al. 2010).

The objective of this research is to examine the complex role of pharmacists in the management and treatment of individuals with mental health disorders, focusing specifically on the principles of pharmaceutical care, effective patient communication, and collaborative efforts across various disciplines.

Methods

This narrative review synthesizes literature published since 2000, evaluating the role of pharmacists in the treatment and management of mental disorders within multidisciplinary healthcare teams. A document from the World Health Organization, released in 1997, outlines the essential professional duties of pharmacists, which encompass effective communication, education and training, delivery of care, informed decision-making, leadership in transformation, and a commitment to lifelong learning. This document serves as the basis for defining the timeline starting

in 2000 in our pursuit of publications pertaining to the topic. A detailed literature search was conducted across various scientific databases, including PubMed, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, Scopus, and Google Scholar. The search utilized combinations of the following keywords: "pharmacist" and "clinical pharmacist" alongside "mental disorders," "depression," "psychiatric conditions," "substance abuse," "mental health promotion," "patient communication," "psychotropic drug interactions," "therapy adherence," "counseling," and "symptom management," to ensure a thorough search. To enhance the search further, we manually examined the references of selected articles to uncover additional pertinent studies.

We excluded studies where the pharmacist's role was not directly associated with the themes of this article. The extensive search process yielded a considerable number of studies, which were subsequently reviewed and analyzed based on their relevance to the specific topics of interest.

Results

Main aspects

The main aspects of pharmacists' roles include counseling and educational services, facilitating adherence to therapy, identifying and managing drug interactions, assessing therapeutic effects, supporting symptom management, and providing confidentiality and empathy.

Counseling and education

Pharmacists deliver comprehensive counseling aimed at enhancing medication adherence while educating patients regarding their treatment regimens, possible side effects, and the significance of adherence (Tai et al. 2014; Panesar 2016; Shepherd et al. 2022). Additionally, they provide specialized education tailored to the unique needs of individual patients, which can greatly improve therapeutic outcomes (Soubolsky and Halpape 2022; Ashcroft et al. 2024). A key aspect to consider is that pharmacists are vital in the treatment and management of mental health disorders, serving as essential members of multidisciplinary healthcare teams. Within these teams, pharmacists engage in case conferencing, collaborative management of drug therapies, and the formulation of care plans (Rubio-Valera et al. 2014; El-Den et al. 2021). Their cooperation with other healthcare professionals, such as physicians and mental health experts, is crucial for delivering comprehensive patient care.

Support for medication adherence

A significant obstacle in the management of mental health disorders is the consistent intake of prescribed medications. Pharmacists play a crucial role in emphasizing the necessity of following the prescribed treatment regimen and providing encouragement to patients, particularly when the benefits of the therapy are not immediately apparent. Additionally, they can engage in discussions

regarding effective strategies to enhance adherence, including the use of reminders and the establishment of suitable daily routines for medication administration. A scoping review conducted in 2023 revealed that interventions led by pharmacists—such as educational initiatives, reminders, and follow-up care—substantially enhanced adherence rates among mental health patients across community, hospital, and interdisciplinary environments (Syrnyk and Glass 2023).

Detecting and managing drug interactions

Pharmacists have the specialized knowledge necessary to recognize and address possible drug interactions, especially those that involve psychiatric medications alongside other medications prescribed at the same time. For instance, some antidepressants may interact with cardiovascular medications or pain relievers, which could require dosage modifications or heightened monitoring. By conducting thorough assessments and providing patient counseling, pharmacists are essential in reducing the risks linked to polypharmacy in mental health treatment (Spina and de Leon 2007).

Monitoring the effects of therapy

Pharmacists play a crucial role in overseeing the outcomes of therapeutic interventions. They assist patients in identifying both the beneficial and adverse effects of their treatment, thereby facilitating the attainment of the most effective therapeutic results. Additionally, pharmacists can

recommend consultations with the prescribing physician for potential dosage modifications or a change of medication if the expected results are not achieved or if severe side effects occur (Soubolsky and Halpape 2022).

Support for symptom management

Pharmacists are positioned to provide alternative strategies for alleviating certain symptoms associated with mental health disorders and the adverse effects of treatments. This can include recommending supplements or offering lifestyle modifications that may enhance the overall well-being of the patient. Pharmacists frequently serve as the initial point of contact within the community and have the potential to contribute to the early identification of mental health concerns. They are capable of assessing patients and directing them to suitable care providers, thereby enabling prompt interventions (Shepherd et al. 2022; Ashcroft et al. 2024).

Assurance of confidentiality and empathy

Pharmacists need to maintain confidentiality and cultivate a trusting environment, allowing patients to share their experiences and concerns openly. Pharmacists encounter numerous obstacles, such as the stigma linked to mental health, lack of adequate knowledge, and conflicting priorities (Rubio-Valera et al. 2014; Panesar 2016; Ashcroft et al. 2024).

The primary roles that pharmacists undertake when consulting with patients suffering from mental health disorders are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. The role of pharmacists in mental health support.

Support for medication adherence

Addressing the issue of patient non-adherence to prescribed mental health therapies presents a significant challenge for pharmacists. Their responsibilities extend beyond providing access to essential medications; they also play a crucial role in encouraging patients to comply with their treatment regimens by elucidating the significance and advantages of such therapies (Osterberg and Blaschke 2005; Syrnyk and Glass 2023). Effective strategies encompass establishing trust, fostering open communication, detailing the benefits and possible risks associated with the medications prescribed by the therapist, developing reminders and structured plans for consistent medication use, monitoring patient progress, and conducting regular follow-up appointments (Osterberg and Blaschke 2005; Brown and Bussell 2011).

Motivational interviewing

Pharmacists aim to establish trusting relationships with patients, which is essential for fostering open communication. By demonstrating empathy and neutrality, they create an environment where patients feel comfortable discussing their worries and challenges. This dialogue often encompasses obstacles such as stigma, adverse effects, or diminished motivation that can influence adherence to medication regimens. One effective approach employed by pharmacists is motivational interviewing, which empowers patients to engage actively in their treatment decisions. Through this technique, pharmacists facilitate discussions that allow patients to articulate their motivations for seeking improvement and to determine the continuation of their therapy.

Regular consultation

Pharmacists play a crucial role in educating patients about the advantages and potential hazards of medication use. They emphasize that adhering to prescribed medication regimens can significantly enhance patients' symptoms and overall quality of life. Additionally, pharmacists highlight the dangers linked to improper or inconsistent medication intake, which may lead to worsened symptoms or complications arising from abrupt cessation of treatment. In instances where patients experience adverse effects, pharmacists are equipped to discuss strategies for symptom management and, if required, can refer patients to their physicians for adjustments in medication or dosage. This proactive approach aims to mitigate any hesitance patients may feel toward continuing their therapy due to negative experiences. Regular consultations between pharmacists and patients are a key element of modern pharmaceutical practice. These interactions aim not only to improve adherence to prescribed therapy but also to optimize clinical outcomes, reduce hospitalizations, and enhance patients' quality of life. The most commonly used approach is the traditional one of conducting personal meetings in the pharmacy. This includes regular conversations with the patient during the receipt of medications

and provides an opportunity to follow up on the therapeutic process and clarify any questions that arise. Another effective form is the planned outpatient consultation, in which the pharmacist offers specific times for individual meetings, similar to a doctor's schedule. These methods assist the patient in correctly understanding the therapy, reduce the risk of medication errors, and ensure better communication. Studies have shown that patients who regularly receive pharmaceutical consultations demonstrate higher levels of adherence to therapy (Osterberg and Blaschke 2005). Furthermore, as technology advances, digital methods of consultation have also entered the market and are becoming a particularly useful alternative, especially for patients in remote areas. Telephone and video consultations have proven effective for conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, and mental disorders. A systematic review shows that digital interventions, including pharmaceutical telephone consultations, significantly improve adherence to therapy and lead to better clinical outcomes (Kruse et al. 2020).

Reminders

The involvement of pharmacists in the management of medication adherence is significant, as they assist in formulating reminders and schedules for the timely intake of prescribed drugs (Klang et al. 2015; McMillan et al. 2018). To promote adherence, pharmacists advocate for the use of mobile applications, weekly pill organizers, or the involvement of family members to bolster the treatment regimen. Furthermore, they often conduct regular follow-up appointments with patients to assess treatment efficacy and identify any required adjustments. This sustained support fosters patient motivation and enhances awareness of their treatment outcomes. Digital health initiatives are effectively enhancing adherence to treatment protocols among individuals with mental health disorders by improving the quality and accessibility of pharmaceutical services (Bhat et al. 2018; Bingham et al. 2020).

Detecting and managing the interactions among psychiatric medications, other pharmaceuticals, and dietary supplements

This aspect is a vital component of the pharmacist's role. Pharmacists employ various strategies to mitigate the potential for adverse effects and to safeguard patient well-being (Freeman et al. 2010). To accurately assess drug interactions, pharmacists use specialized software and databases, such as Lexicomp, Micromedex, and UpToDate. These systems provide reliable information on the mechanism, severity, and clinical significance of interactions, as well as recommendations for their management (Vandenbroucke et al. 2012). Furthermore, to reduce the likelihood of adverse interactions, pharmacists evaluate not only the medications prescribed and their respective dosages but also consider individual patient characteristics, including age, weight, comorbidities, and

lifestyle choices. This assessment is particularly crucial for patients with mental health conditions, who frequently utilize various medications and supplements, often without professional guidance. Pharmacists remain vigilant for indicators of such interactions, including dizziness, fluctuations in mood, sedation, or gastrointestinal disturbances (Moini and Ross 2019). A 2022 study shows that pharmacists significantly contribute to the detection of clinically relevant interactions that often go unnoticed in routine practice. The inclusion of a pharmacist in the multidisciplinary team improves the safety of pharmacotherapy and reduces the risk of adverse reactions in psychiatric patients (Joel 2022).

Consultations about supplement use

Pharmacists frequently engage in discussions about the various supplements and natural products that patients may be consuming, including St. John's wort, omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins, and minerals. Of particular concern is St. John's wort (*Hypericum perforatum*), which induces cytochrome P450 enzymes (particularly CYP3A4), reducing plasma levels of many psychotropic drugs. Additionally, when combined with antidepressants containing serotonergic mechanisms, there is a risk of serotonin syndrome (Izzo and Ernst 2009). Pharmacists actively inform patients about the risks associated with introducing new medications or supplements without prior consultation with a healthcare professional. Furthermore, several dietary supplements and herbal products can function as inducers or inhibitors of hepatic enzyme systems that are crucial for drug metabolism. For instance, St. John's wort, broccoli, Brussels sprouts, cauliflower, caffeine, and essential oils derived from rosemary and garlic are recognized as inducers of CYP450 isoenzymes, potentially diminishing the efficacy of concurrent drug therapy (Izzo and Ernst 2009). In contrast, herbs such as ginkgo biloba, red grapefruit, valerian, hops, and milk thistle exhibit inhibitory properties and may result in the accumulation and possible toxicity of specific medications (Gurley et al. 2004).

Consultations about combinations with other pharmaceuticals, including psychotropic medicines

A variety of clinically relevant drug interactions have been documented, occurring at both pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic levels (Wijesinghe 2016). Lithium salts are recognized as pharmacological agents with a narrow therapeutic index. Classical neuroleptics, which interact with various targets, are also included in this category, alongside numerous other medications. Tricyclic antidepressants are associated with cardiotoxic effects in cases of overdose and are readily available, raising concerns regarding potential suicide attempts. Recent advancements in antipsychotic medications that have been integrated into clinical practice in recent years may interact with other psychotropic drugs or medications prescribed for concurrent physical health conditions. The majority of pharmacokinetic interactions associated

with these newer antipsychotics take place at the metabolic level, typically involving alterations in the function of key drug-metabolizing enzymes responsible for their biotransformation, specifically cytochrome P450 (CYP) monooxygenases and/or uridine diphosphate-glucuronosyltransferases (Spina and de Leon 2007). Among modern antidepressants, selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) present a risk for serotonin syndrome when combined improperly with certain foods, supplements, or other medications, and they may increase the risk of suicide in younger individuals. Furthermore, the concurrent use of alcohol with long-term pharmacotherapy can alter drug efficacy; alcohol acts as an inducer of drug-metabolizing enzymes with regular consumption, while it functions as an inhibitor when consumed in a single instance.

Methodological strategy for advising on the combined use of different medications

- **Information collection and evaluation of herbal product usage.** Pharmacists meticulously collect data regarding the patient's consumption of herbal and alternative remedies, including St. John's wort, valerian, ginkgo biloba, ginger, garlic, and melatonin. They assess the dosage, frequency of administration, and whether these products are being used in conjunction with prescribed medications. This information is essential for evaluating potential drug interactions.
- **Detection of possible interactions and hazards.** Numerous herbal products have the potential to interact with antidepressants and other psychotropic drugs. For instance, St. John's wort, frequently utilized for managing depression, can lead to significant interactions with antidepressants and antipsychotics, heightening the risk of serotonin syndrome. Pharmacists utilize databases to identify such interactions and provide warnings to the patient. For example, valerian extract is commonly used for the management of anxiety and insomnia, and it frequently interacts with sedative-hypnotic medications. Melatonin is employed in the treatment of sleep disorders and is often administered alongside antidepressants or antipsychotics; however, its use requires monitoring.
- **Education and awareness for patients.** Pharmacists elucidate the mechanisms of herbal products and their possible effects and limitations to the patient. They should inform patients that although herbal remedies are often perceived as "natural," they are not inherently safe and should be approached with caution, particularly in the context of chronic illnesses or concurrent medications. Pharmacists advise patients to adhere to established guidelines for the safe use and dosage of herbal products, particularly those that may induce adverse effects. They may suggest initiating treatment with lower doses and monitoring for potential side effects while maintaining regular communication with the pharmacist.

- **Encouraging transparent communication.** To foster trust and obtain comprehensive information from the patient, pharmacists must highlight the significance of transparency. Some patients may be reluctant to disclose their use of alternative products, necessitating reassurance that the pharmacist's role is to assist rather than judge their choices.
- **Ongoing monitoring.** Pharmacists should encourage patients to schedule regular follow-ups and report any changes in their health status, as well as the outcomes of alternative therapies. This practice enables pharmacists to evaluate the efficacy of herbal interventions.

A proposal for a systematic, comprehensive guide on pharmaceutical care—providing advice regarding the combined use of psychotropic medications in individuals with mental health disorders, based on updated guidelines—is available in the Suppl. material 1: S1.

The pharmacist's challenges in communicating with patients with mental health conditions

Pharmacists frequently encounter challenges in their interactions with patients suffering from mental health disorders. Successful communication requires particular skills and an understanding of the distinct needs and situations of these individuals.

Challenges in comprehending and processing information, or hindered communication

Certain psychiatric conditions, including schizophrenia and bipolar disorder, frequently present cognitive impairments that hinder patients' ability to comprehend intricate medication details, such as dosage, potential side effects, and drug interactions (Millan et al. 2012). This situation creates significant obstacles for pharmaceutical counseling and underscores the necessity for customized communication strategies, employing straightforward and lucid language, along with the repetition and verification of understanding through methods such as the "teach-back" technique (O'Reilly et al. 2010). It is essential for pharmacists to adopt a patient and organized approach, integrating both verbal and visual aids to support patients with cognitive challenges in effectively managing their treatment (Morrison et al. 2018). In these scenarios, effective communication not only enhances adherence to therapy but also minimizes the likelihood of medication errors.

Noncompliance with prescribed treatment, lack of motivation

Adherence to medication presents a prevalent challenge for individuals suffering from psychiatric disorders. Contributing factors include adverse drug reactions, personal perceptions of ineffectiveness, psychopathological symptoms such as apathy or diminished motivation, and cognitive deficits that result in forgetfulness (Kane et al. 2013). These elements collectively hinder the ability to sustain long-term

adherence to treatment. Pharmacists are essential in mitigating this issue by overseeing adherence, fostering trust, and providing tailored strategies. Such strategies may involve electronic reminders, dosing containers, structured medication regimens, and motivational interviewing designed to bolster the patient's intrinsic motivation (Brown and Bussell 2011). Furthermore, educating patients and maintaining an ongoing dialogue regarding the advantages of therapy and setting realistic expectations can greatly enhance treatment adherence (Osterberg and Blaschke 2005).

Inadequate communication abilities during crises, lack of focus

In periods of mental health crises or when symptoms intensify, individuals suffering from mental health disorders often exhibit manifestations of anxiety, irritability, aggression, or emotional instability. These behaviors can hinder effective communication with healthcare professionals, including pharmacists. This necessitates that pharmacists develop particular crisis communication competencies such as patience, active listening, emotional steadiness, and empathy. Utilizing a calm tone, demonstrating open body language, and steering clear of confrontational remarks have proven to be successful de-escalation techniques in high-risk scenarios (Moore et al. 2018). Ensuring a secure environment and offering clear and predictable instructions also contribute to fostering trust and collaboration, even in the acute stages of a mental health disorder.

The role of pharmacists in providing consultation and education to the public regarding mental health care

Pharmacists are instrumental in enhancing public understanding and education regarding mental health. In addition to providing individualized patient counseling, pharmacists are increasingly engaging in prevention and educational initiatives aimed at reducing the stigma linked to mental health issues and promoting open conversations about the topic (Kremin 2023). As stated by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Pharmaceutical Federation (FIP), the contemporary pharmacist's role extends well beyond the conventional task of dispensing medications. The document WHO/PHARM/97/599 delineates essential professional responsibilities that encompass effective communication, training and education, care provision, informed decision-making, leadership in change, and commitment to lifelong learning (World Health Organization 1997). These responsibilities provide a framework for the proactive involvement of pharmacists within the community, particularly in the realms of mental health and educational assistance (International Pharmaceutical Federation 2020).

Key aspects of the pharmacist's role in public education:

- **Enhancing awareness of mental health.** In countries such as the United States and Canada, pharmacists play a key role in raising public awareness about

mental health. They participate in national and regional public health programs, use digital educational tools, and disseminate information about anxiety, depression, and stress (National Institute of Mental Health 2025). By participating in mental health campaigns and events, pharmacists contribute to improving public understanding of the importance of early intervention and access to treatment.

- **Instruction on the appropriate use of psychotropic medications.** Pharmacists offer essential advice to patients and their families concerning the appropriate use of psychotropic medications, which encompasses dosage, length of treatment, possible drug interactions (such as with alcohol or tyramine), and adverse effects. They stress the importance of rigorous compliance with the prescribed treatment regimen to ensure stabilization of the condition and to avert relapse.
- **Addressing stigma and promoting early intervention.** The stigma associated with mental illness frequently discourages individuals from pursuing assistance. In the UK, pharmacists participate in initiatives and programs designed to diminish stigma and facilitate informed communication with patients experiencing mental health issues (Royal Pharmaceutical Society 2018). They actively advocate for a constructive perspective on mental health and clarify that these conditions are manageable just like any other medical ailment.
- **Supporting mental health initiatives and preventive programs.** Pharmacists are involved in preventive initiatives addressing risk factors such as stress, substance abuse, and sleep disorders. As part of these programs, they conduct informational sessions and facilitate the distribution of materials that educate the public on effective stress management techniques and strategies to enhance mental well-being.
- **Referrals to additional professionals and resources.** Pharmacists assist patients in accessing essential resources by referring them to psychologists, psychiatrists, and mental health support services. They provide information about local resources, including crisis hotlines and self-help groups.
- **Engagement in digital and online educational programs.** Pharmacists are increasingly leveraging online platforms and social media to share information regarding mental health. This encompasses awareness initiatives, webinars, e-newsletters, and publications directed toward the general populace. In different areas, pharmacists are engaging in online campaigns and employing social media channels to spread knowledge pertaining to mental health education.

In Bulgaria, the role of pharmacists in the field of mental health is developing. There are initiatives by pharmacies and professional organizations to provide educational information and consultations. The Ministry of Health's document on national mental health policy (2004–2012)

emphasizes the need for inter-institutional cooperation, including with the pharmaceutical sector (Ministry of Health 2004–2012).

Suggested methodology for certain particular conditions

Approach in patients with depressive conditions

Pharmacists can be instrumental in elevating a patient's quality of life and facilitating their path to recovery (Kamusheva et al. 2020). Addressing the needs of a patient in a state of depression demands a comprehensive and thoughtful approach that encompasses not only the prescription and administration of medication but also the provision of support during the therapeutic process (see Suppl. material 1: S2).

- **Guidance on the appropriate administration of antidepressants.** Pharmacists offer patients detailed information regarding their prescribed medications, including the timing and method of ingestion, as well as anticipated outcomes. They clarify that the therapeutic effects of antidepressants typically manifest within a period of 2 to 4 weeks, which is crucial for sustaining the patient's motivation during the initial treatment phase (Capoccia et al. 2004; Brown and Bussell 2011).
- **Clarification of potential adverse effects** associated with the medications and strategies for their management (Kelly et al. 2008). Patients may be deterred from continuing their treatment due to common side effects of antidepressants, such as sedation or sexual dysfunction. Sexual dysfunction represents a relatively unexplored negative consequence of antidepressant medications and may elevate the likelihood of treatment discontinuation and non-adherence to antidepressant therapy (Higgins et al. 2010; Clayton et al. 2014; Jing and Straw-Wilson 2016). Pharmacists provide insights into these possible side effects, explore methods to alleviate discomfort, and advise on when it is necessary to seek medical assistance if the side effects become excessively severe.
- **Monitoring the patient's condition and providing emotional support.** During each consultation, pharmacists can assess the patient's condition and inquire about both physical and emotional well-being. Encouraging patients to communicate any perceived changes in their health, whether positive or negative, is essential. Additionally, pharmacists can provide guidance on managing everyday stress and anxiety. When appropriate, they may also refer patients to mental health professionals, such as psychologists or psychiatrists, for more specialized assistance (Chavez and Kosirog 2019).
- **Assessing potential drug interactions.** Numerous individuals diagnosed with depression concurrently utilize additional medications that could potentially

interact with antidepressants. Pharmacists are responsible for identifying possible interactions and providing guidance to patients regarding particular drug or food combinations that should be avoided, including the combination of MAOIs and foods high in tyramine (Rieck and Kim 2014).

- **Educational initiatives focused on managing depressive symptoms.** Pharmacists can enhance community well-being by facilitating brief educational initiatives aimed at managing depressive symptoms and stress. These sessions may include guidance on maintaining a healthy lifestyle, engaging in physical exercise, adhering to a balanced diet, and establishing a daily routine conducive to mental well-being. Bingham et al. (2019) emphasized the importance of pharmacist participation, indicating the possibility of enhanced nutrition, increased physical activity, and better sleep for patients with mental health conditions, particularly in the short term (Bingham et al. 2019).
- **Recognizing potential indicators of suicide risk.** Individuals suffering from depression are particularly vulnerable to suicidal thoughts, especially during the early phases of treatment when the initiation of antidepressants may lead to increased energy levels prior to mood improvement. Pharmacists should be vigilant for signs such as mood fluctuations, expressions of hopelessness, and alterations in behavior (Fergusson et al. 2005). Upon observing these indicators, it is imperative to refer the patient to emergency medical services.

Approach in individuals exhibiting dependence on psychoactive substances

The role of pharmacists in assisting patients with addictions requires a compassionate, empathetic, and nonjudgmental demeanor, alongside adherence to professional ethics and expertise in motivational interviewing techniques, brief interventions, and appropriate treatment referrals. Individuals suffering from substance use disorders frequently encounter complex medical, behavioral, and social obstacles, which may include stigma, coexisting mental health issues, and social marginalization (Babor 2018).

Pharmacists, especially those working in community and hospital environments, are positioned to provide educational, therapeutic, and motivational assistance as part of a collaborative care model. This encompasses the identification of risky behaviors, referrals for medication-assisted treatment (MAT), and the dissemination of information regarding the safety and efficacy of various treatment modalities, including naltrexone, methadone, or buprenorphine (National Institute on Drug Abuse 2023).

Key strategies for counseling patients with addictions (see Suppl. material 1: S3):

- **Recognizing indicators of addiction.** Indicators that may suggest the presence of addiction include a heightened frequency of requests for prescribed medications (such as opioids or benzodiazepines), premature requests for new prescriptions, or claims

of lost medications, as well as shopping between different pharmacies (“doctor/pharmacy shopping”). It is essential to approach these situations with sensitivity, exercising discretion and avoiding premature judgments (Cochran et al. 2017).

- **Educating on safety and risk factors.** It is crucial to inform patients about the dangers associated with prolonged use and improper dosages of psychoactive substances. Implementing harm reduction strategies, including strict adherence to prescribed dosages and the avoidance of combining specific medications with alcohol or other substances, can be advantageous (American Society of Health-System Pharmacists 2019).
- **Support for cessation and motivational interviewing.** Motivational interviewing assists patients in recognizing their addiction issues and fostering their motivation for change. Pharmacists should employ open-ended questions that encourage patients to contemplate the potential repercussions of their addiction while providing support throughout the decision-making process. Ensuring discretion and maintaining confidentiality are paramount in creating a supportive atmosphere for patients (Lindson et al. 2023). Adopting a nonjudgmental demeanor fosters trust and facilitates open dialogue. An empathetic approach is fundamental in encouraging patients to communicate candidly (International Pharmaceutical Federation 2019).
- **Support with maintenance medication therapy.** Patients dealing with opioid or other substance addictions may be prescribed maintenance medications, such as methadone or buprenorphine. Pharmacists play a critical role in monitoring these patients and can offer guidance on the appropriate use and possible side effects of these treatments (Wakeman and Barnett 2018; Winstanley and Clark 2018).
- **Referrals to specialized assistance and resources.** Pharmacists can guide patients toward addiction specialists, including psychiatrists, counselors, or rehabilitation programs. Additionally, they may provide information about hotlines or support services that offer counseling or assistance for addiction (Rubio-Valera et al. 2014).

The engagement of clinical pharmacists in the hospital-based therapeutic care of patients experiencing mental health issues

The clinical pharmacist holds a crucial position in the multidisciplinary management of patients suffering from mental health disorders within the hospital environment. Their specialized knowledge in pharmacotherapy is essential to ensure the safe, effective, and personalized use of psychotropic medicines within hospital mental health services. Through this collaborative effort, clinical pharmacists play a significant role in enhancing therapeutic outcomes, ensuring patient safety, and promoting adherence to psychiatric treatment plans (Rubio-Valera et al. 2014).

Although the organization and execution of clinical pharmacy services differ worldwide, numerous healthcare systems are increasingly acknowledging the pharmacist as a vital element of inpatient mental health care. Nations such as the United Kingdom, Canada, and Australia have well-established clinical pharmacy practices in psychiatric units, where pharmacists engage in medication reconciliation, treatment planning, and psychoeducation (Finley et al. 2003).

In Bulgaria, the clinical pharmacy profession is currently undergoing gradual integration. National initiatives are ongoing to improve hospital-based pharmaceutical care through the establishment of clinical pharmacist roles and the formulation of protocols for collaborative practice. These initiatives align with European recommendations aimed at broadening the pharmacist's responsibilities in psychiatry and enhancing the continuity of care for patients with complex mental health requirements (Ministry of Health 2020).

Main responsibilities of the clinical pharmacist in psychiatric care include the following:

- **Assessment of pharmacotherapy and management of drug interactions.** In psychiatric care environments, the clinical pharmacist plays a crucial role in assessing pharmacotherapeutic regimens to detect and address possible drug-drug interactions, duplications, and contraindications. Particular emphasis is placed on the intricate pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of psychiatric medications, especially in situations involving polypharmacy. Furthermore, the pharmacist evaluates interactions between psychotropic medications and non-psychiatric drugs or dietary supplements that patients might be using simultaneously, such as St. John's wort, omega-3 fatty acids, or over-the-counter products, which could influence the effectiveness or safety of the treatment (Spina and de Leon 2007).
- **Development of personalized treatment strategies.** Clinical pharmacists work in conjunction with psychiatrists, nurses, and other healthcare professionals to create personalized treatment plans that take into account the patient's diagnosis, treatment history, comorbidities, and reactions to prior therapies. They play a crucial role in:
 - Adjusting psychotropic dosages for therapeutic efficacy
 - Monitoring therapeutic drug levels (e.g., lithium, valproate)
 - Addressing medication resistance or sensitivity
 - Reducing the risk of side effects, such as sedation, metabolic disturbances, or extrapyramidal symptoms

Their expertise contributes to therapeutic drug monitoring, pharmacogenetic considerations, and the rational selection of alternative regimens in complex or treatment-resistant cases (Finley et al. 2003).

- **Monitoring treatment efficacy and patient status.** Clinical pharmacists are integral to the ongoing monitoring of therapeutic outcomes in hospitalized patients receiving psychotropic medications.

Their role involves systematic documentation of clinical responses, including improvement in psychiatric symptoms, stabilization of mood, or reduction in agitation or psychosis. They also monitor for early signs of adverse drug reactions, toxicity, or insufficient therapeutic effect, enabling timely adjustments to the regimen. Additionally, pharmacists play a key role in the management of medication discontinuation, where they observe for withdrawal symptoms and ensure that tapering protocols are followed appropriately to minimize clinical deterioration or rebound effects. In many hospital systems, their direct collaboration with the care team enhances real-time decision-making and supports safer transitions between pharmacologic phases (e.g., initiation, maintenance, and discontinuation) (Rubio-Valera et al. 2014).

- **Providing guidance to patients and their families.** Clinical pharmacists act as readily available educators for patients and their caregivers, providing clear, evidence-based advice on the proper use of prescribed psychotropic medications. They highlight the significance of adhering to medication regimens, clarify dosing schedules, and address common issues related to effectiveness, side effects, and treatment expectations. Moreover, they assist in dispelling myths surrounding psychiatric medications and promote open discussions about potential concerns, which is essential for encouraging informed, stigma-free engagement in long-term mental health care (O'Reilly et al. 2010).
- **Training healthcare professionals.** Clinical pharmacists play a crucial educational role within multidisciplinary teams, aiding in the continuous training and professional growth of physicians, nurses, and allied healthcare professionals. They provide insights on new psychopharmacological agents, the rollout of psychotropic pharmacogenomics, revised clinical guidelines, and methods to reduce medication-related errors in psychiatric care. Through in-service presentations, case discussions, and the development of protocols, pharmacists improve evidence-based medication practices and encourage adherence to optimal standards in psychiatric pharmacotherapy. In nations such as the United States, Australia, and certain regions of Europe, clinical pharmacists have clearly defined responsibilities within mental health facilities, directly contributing to protocol education and enhancing team efficacy (Eaves et al. 2020; El-Den et al. 2021; Farag et al. 2022).

The role of the clinical pharmacist in the therapy of patients with mental disorders is summarized in Fig. 2.

In Bulgaria, the role of clinical pharmacists within hospital settings is still in a developmental phase, with ongoing institutional and educational efforts aimed at formally integrating clinical pharmacy services into multidisciplinary care models (Getov et al. 2013). Although the number of clinical pharmacists with specialization in psychiatric care remains limited, their presence in hospitals is gradually expanding, particularly in tertiary and university-affiliated medical centers.

Figure 2. The role of clinical pharmacists in the hospital-based therapeutic care of patients with mental disorders.

Discussion and future perspectives

The increasing intricacy of mental health care highlights the pressing necessity for specialized training programs specifically designed for pharmacists. Patients diagnosed with mental health disorders frequently require individualized therapeutic approaches and sensitive, well-informed communication, which necessitate advanced skills that extend beyond conventional pharmaceutical education. The justification for such training is multifaceted. Pharmacists who interact with individuals experiencing mental illness must cultivate a profound comprehension of psychiatric disorders, treatment options, and psychopharmacological concepts, alongside expertise in motivational interviewing, crisis communication, and medication management. Furthermore, they must be equipped to address challenges associated with adherence, polypharmacy, and adverse drug reactions, which are prevalent in psychiatric environments.

Training initiatives may be organized by professional bodies, academic institutions, or healthcare organizations, generally covering topics such as recognizing symptoms of mental disorders, effective communication strategies with patients, and techniques to support their treatment.

Several nations have begun to implement specialized training programs for pharmacists in the realm of mental health care:

- United States.** The American Pharmacists Association (APhA) provides a range of programs, such as Mental Health First Aid, which empowers pharmacists to recognize early warning signs, offer initial support, and make suitable referrals. Additionally, numerous U.S. universities incorporate psychiatric pharmacy modules into their postgraduate pharmacy program.
- United Kingdom.** The Royal Pharmaceutical Society (RPS) has established a Mental Health Pharmacy Competency Framework, encompassing training in therapeutic management, communication skills, and clinical assessment. This framework is designed to enhance pharmacists' capacity to deliver safe and effective care to patients suffering from psychiatric disorders.
- Australia.** The Pharmaceutical Society of Australia (PSA) offers advanced courses and practical training for pharmacists who assist patients diagnosed with depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, and schizophrenia. The training curriculum includes clinical communication, psychological support techniques, and crisis intervention strategies.
- Canada.** The Canadian Society of Hospital Pharmacists (CSHP) provides training that focuses on medication therapy management in psychiatric care, particularly for pharmacists working in hospital mental health units. These programs stress the importance

of recognizing psychiatric symptoms and tailoring pharmacological treatments to individual needs.

- **Bulgaria.** Although still in its early stages, there are efforts to incorporate mental health communication into pharmacy education. For example, the Medical University of Plovdiv offers a specialized course titled *Psychopharmacology and pharmacopsychiatry*, which includes training on communication with mentally ill patients, as part of its Pharmacist Assistant curriculum (Medical University of Plovdiv 2020). This indicates a growing recognition of the necessity to equip pharmacists for effective interaction with this patient demographic.

Improved education in psychiatric pharmacy can greatly enhance the quality of interactions between patients and pharmacists, resulting in increased treatment adherence, earlier detection of relapses or complications, and a decrease in the stigma associated with mental illness.

Pharmaceutical care represents a patient-centered practice model wherein the pharmacist takes on the responsibility for a patient's medication-related needs and is accountable for this obligation. In the realm of mental health disorders, pharmaceutical care involves not only the precise dispensing and monitoring of psychotropic medications but also collaboration with other healthcare professionals to ensure that therapeutic objectives are met, side effects are minimized, and the patient's quality of life is improved through ongoing, personalized follow-up. Innovative frameworks that may improve the function of pharmacists include integrated mental health-pharmacy collaborative care models, the incorporation of pharmacists into primary care mental health teams, and the application of pharmacogenomic-guided therapy modifications to tailor treatment.

Recognized research deficiencies include the necessity for standardized outcome metrics to evaluate the effects of pharmacist interventions in mental health, an increase in interventional studies across varied healthcare environments, and the investigation of digital resources in pharmaceutical care for psychiatric patients.

The strengths of this research lie in its thorough compilation of existing international practices and guidelines, its emphasis on the roles of both hospital and community pharmacies, and the incorporation of patient communication techniques. However, limitations include the lack of extensive empirical data from Bulgarian practices and the restricted assessment of long-term patient outcomes. In addition, while existing guidelines lay the groundwork for pharmacist participation in the management of mental health disorders, significant research deficiencies persist that require further investigation. For example, the majority of existing studies focus on optimizing medication and supporting adherence; however, there is a scarcity of evidence regarding the wider psychosocial roles that pharmacists could fulfill as integral members of multidisciplinary teams. Future studies should explore innovative collaborative models involving pharmacists, physicians,

psychologists, and community organizations that address not only pharmacotherapy but also patient education, stigma reduction, and long-term recovery outcomes.

Furthermore, the creation of new frameworks that expand pharmacists' responsibilities beyond conventional dispensing roles could amplify their influence. Digital health platforms, collaborative care models, and structured training in mental health first aid are promising directions. These frameworks could facilitate the systematic integration of pharmacists and their collaborators into mental health care pathways, thus promoting early detection, continuity of care, and crisis intervention.

In this regard, our supplementary materials aim to address some of these deficiencies by providing practical recommendations: (i) a systematic, comprehensive guide on pharmaceutical care with targeted advice on the combined use of psychotropic medications for individuals with mental health disorders, (ii) a framework for the management and pharmaceutical care of patients suffering from depression, and (iii) a framework for the management and pharmaceutical care of patients with psychoactive substance addiction. These resources are designed to serve as foundational tools for the development of standardized, evidence-based instruments that can assist pharmacists and their collaborators in delivering more effective and coordinated mental health care.

Conclusion

Pharmacists are increasingly recognized as essential contributors to the care of individuals with mental health disorders, extending their responsibilities well beyond the conventional role of medication dispensing. They enhance therapeutic outcomes by providing patient education and counseling, encouraging adherence to treatment, identifying and managing drug interactions, monitoring both efficacy and side effects, and offering crisis support. Concurrently, they are instrumental in diminishing stigma and promoting health literacy within the community.

Globally, effective practices have already been established for the integration of pharmacists into multidisciplinary teams, as well as for the creation of specialized training programs aimed at improving competencies in psychopharmacology, crisis communication, and motivational interviewing. In Bulgaria, this role is gradually evolving, with current initiatives underscoring the necessity for more structured policies, protocols, and educational modules to guarantee the sustainable and effective implementation of pharmaceutical care in mental health.

Future initiatives should prioritize the development of standardized tools for evaluating the impact of pharmaceutical interventions, the adoption of digital solutions for remote consultations, and the formulation of integrated models for collaboration with physicians, psychologists, and social services. These measures will facilitate the early identification of deterioration, mitigate the risk of adverse interactions, and enhance the trust between patients and pharmacists.

In this framework, pharmacists should be viewed not merely as medication experts but as proactive partners in the comprehensive treatment and recovery process for patients with mental disorders—a partnership that will become increasingly vital in the contemporary healthcare landscape.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

References

- American Society of Health-System Pharmacists (ASHP) (2019) ASHP Guidelines on the Pharmacist's Role in Substance Use Prevention and Education. *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy* 76(5): 356–367. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajhp/zxy080>
- Ashcroft R, Mathers A, Gin A, Lam S, Donnelly C, Brown JB, Kourgiantakis T, Mehta K, Rayner J, Sur D, Adamson K, Kirvan A, Dolovich L (2024) Pharmacists' role and experiences with delivering mental health care within team-based primary care settings during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Pharmacy Practice* 32(2): 156–163. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ijpp/riad086>
- Babor TF, Caetano R, Casswell S, Edwards G, Giesbrecht N, Graham K, Rossow I (2010) *Alcohol: No Ordinary Commodity: Research and Public Policy*, 2nd edn (Oxford, 2010; online edn, Oxford Academic, 1 May 2010). <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199551149.001.0001>
- Bhat S, Kroehl ME, Trinkley KE, Chow Z, Heath LJ, Billups SJ, Loeb DF (2018) Evaluation of a Clinical Pharmacist-Led Multidisciplinary Antidepressant Telemonitoring Service in the Primary Care Setting. *Population Health Management* 21(5): 366–372. <https://doi.org/10.1089/pop.2017.0144>
- Bingham J, Axon DR, Scovis N, Taylor AM (2018) Evaluating the effectiveness of clinical pharmacy consultations on nutrition, physical activity, and sleep in improving patient-reported psychiatric outcomes for individuals with mental illnesses. *Pharmacy (Basel)* 7(1): 2. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmacy7010002>
- Bingham J, Silva-Almodóvar A, Lee H, Benson C, Michael R, Azurin CM, Taylor AM (2020) The role of the pharmacist in mental health: An investigation of the impact of pharmacist-led interventions on psychotropic medication adherence in patients with diabetes. *Journal of the American Pharmacists Association: JAPhA* 60(4): e58–e63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japh.2020.01.009>
- Brown MT, Bussell JK (2011) Medication adherence: WHO cares? *Mayo Clinic Proceedings* 86(4): 304–314. <https://doi.org/10.4065/mcp.2010.0575>
- Capoccia K, Boudreau D, Blough D, Ellsworth A, Clark D, Stevens N, Katon W, Sullivan S (2004) Randomised trial of pharmacist interventions to improve depression care and outcomes in primary care. *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy* 61(4): 364–372. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajhp/61.4.364>
- Chavez B, Kosirog E (2019) Impact on an integrated psychiatric pharmacy service in a primary care clinic. *The Mental Health Clinician* 9(4): 269–274. <https://doi.org/10.9740/mhc.2019.07.269>
- Chen T (2008) Community pharmacy's role in managing mental illness. *Australian Journal of Pharmacy* 89(1058): 74–76.
- Clayton AH, Croft HA, Handiwala L (2014) Antidepressants and sexual dysfunction: mechanisms and clinical implications. *Postgraduate Medicine* 126(2): 91–99. <https://doi.org/10.3810/pgm.2014.03.2744>
- Cochran G, Gordon AJ, Lo-Ciganic W (2017) Prescription opioid misuse: Pharmacists' role in preventing abuse. *Journal of the American Pharmacists Association* 57(2): S67–S72.e2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japh.2017.01.010>
- Eaves S, Gonzalvo J, Hamm JA, Williams G, Ott C (2020) The evolving role of the pharmacist for individuals with serious mental illness. *Journal of the American Pharmacists Association* 60(5): S11–4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japh.2020.04.017>
- El-Den S, Collins JC, Chen TF, O'Reilly CL (2021) Pharmacists' roles in mental healthcare: Past, present and future. *Pharmacy Practice* 19(3): 2545. <https://doi.org/10.18549/PharmPract.2021.3.2545>
- Farag M, Chalmers L, Hoti K, Hughes J (2022) The role of the clinical pharmacist in mental health hospital-in-the-home: A scoping review. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy* 18(10): 3724–3735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2022.04.004>

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

- Fergusson D, Doucette S, Glass KC, Shapiro S, Healy D, Hebert P, Hutton B (2005) Association between suicide attempts and selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors: systematic review of randomized controlled trials. *BMJ* 330(7488): 396. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.330.7488.396>
- Finley PR, Crismon ML, Rush AJ (2003) Evaluating the impact of pharmacists in mental health: A systematic review. *Pharmacotherapy* 23(12): 1634–1644. <https://doi.org/10.1592/phco.23.15.1634.63502>
- Fleischhacker WW, Uchida H (2014) Critical review of antipsychotic polypharmacy in the treatment of schizophrenia, *International Journal of Neuropsychopharmacology* 17(7): 1083–1093. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1461145712000399>
- Foong AL, Grindrod KA, Patel T, Kellar J (2018) Demystifying serotonin syndrome (or serotonin toxicity). *Canadian Family Physician* 64(10): 720–727.
- Freeman MP, Fava M, Lake J, Trivedi MH, Wisner KL, Mischoulon D (2010) Complementary and alternative medicine in major depressive disorder: the American Psychiatric Association Task Force report. *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry* 71(6): 669–681. <https://doi.org/10.4088/JCP.10cs05959blu>
- Getov I, Kostov E, Lebanova H, Grigorov E (2013) Clinical pharmacy – essence, progress and challenges in practice. *Medicinski Pregled* 49(3): 30–37.
- Gurley BJ, Gardner SF, Hubbard MA, Williams DK, Gentry WB, Carrier J, Khan IA, Edwards DJ, Shah A (2004) In vivo assessment of botanical supplementation on human cytochrome P450 phenotypes: Citrus aurantium, Echinacea purpurea, milk thistle, and saw palmetto. *Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics* 76(5): 428–440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clpt.2004.07.007>
- Higgins A, Nash M, Lynch AM (2010) Antidepressant-associated sexual dysfunction: impact, effects, and treatment. *Drug, Healthcare and Patient Safety* 2: 141–150. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DHPS.S7634>
- International Pharmaceutical Federation (FIP) (2019) Pharmacy's role in harm reduction. <https://www.fip.org/file/4325> [Accessed 25.02.2025]
- International Pharmaceutical Federation (FIP) (2020) Development Goals for Pharmacy Education and Workforce. <https://www.fip.org/development-goals> [Accessed 15.05.2025]
- Izzo AA, Ernst E (2009) Interactions between herbal medicines and prescribed drugs: an updated systematic review. *Drugs* 69(13): 1777–1798. <https://doi.org/10.2165/11317010-000000000-00000>
- Jing E, Straw-Wilson K (2016) Sexual dysfunction in selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) and potential solutions: A narrative literature review. *The Mental Health Clinician* 6(4): 191–196. <https://doi.org/10.9740/mhc.2016.07.191>
- Joel J (2022) A Clinical Pharmacist-Led Study of Drug-Drug Interactions in Patients with Psychiatric Disorders. *Journal of Cellular and Molecular Pharmacology* 6(4): 130.
- Kamusheva M, Ignatova D, Golda A, Skowron A (2020) The potential role of the pharmacist in supporting patients with depression – A literature-based point of view. *Integrated Pharmacy Research and Practice* 9: 49–63. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IPRPS.S239672>
- Kane JM, Kishimoto T, Correll CU (2013) Non-adherence to medication in patients with psychotic disorders: epidemiology, contributing factors and management strategies. *World Psychiatry* 12(3): 216–226. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.20060>
- Karolewicz B, Nowak M, Gawin A, Milejski P, Owczarek A (2020) Identification of the area services provided by a pharmacist in the care of patients with mental health problems: Conditions, possibilities of care providing, and the needs of patients. *Acta Poloniae Pharmaceutica – Drug Research* 77(5): 281–296. <https://doi.org/10.32383/farm-pol/125320>
- Kelly K, Posternak M, Alpert JE (2008) Toward achieving optimal response: understanding and managing antidepressant side effects. *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience* 10(4): 409–418. <https://doi.org/10.31887/DCNS.2008.10.4/kkelly>
- Khartabil N, Haghparast P, Al-Chokachi Z, Clemens E (2024) The impact of pharmacists on medication safety in mental health: A narrative review. *JACCP: Journal of the American College of Clinical Pharmacy* 7(2): 177–189. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jac5.1900>
- Klang SH, Ben-Amnon Y, Cohen Y, Barak Y (2015) Community pharmacists' support improves antidepressant adherence in the community. *International Clinical Psychopharmacology* 30(6): 316–319. <https://doi.org/10.1097/YIC.000000000000090>
- Kremin Y, Lesyk L, Lesyk R, Levytska O, Khromovych B (2023) Detailing the ten essential professional roles of the pharmacist to ensure the scope of professional functions. *Scientia Pharmaceutica* 91(1): 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/scipharm91010005>
- Lindson N, Richards-Doran D, Heath L, Hartmann-Boyce J (2023) Motivational interviewing for substance use. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* (12): 1–219. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD008063.pub3>
- McMillan SS, Kelly F, Hattingh HL, Fowler JL, Mihala G, Wheeler AJ (2018) The impact of a person-centred community pharmacy mental health medication support service on consumer outcomes. *Journal of Mental Health* 27(2): 164–173. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638237.2017.1340618>
- Medical University of Plovdiv (2020) Curriculum for the specialization “Pharmacist Assistant”. https://mu-plovdiv.bg/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/uchebni_programi_spetsialnost_spetsialnost_pomoshtnik_farmacevt.pdf#page=363 [Accessed 01.03.2025]
- Millan MJ, Agid Y, Brüne M, Bullmore ET, Carter CS, Clayton NS, Connor R, Davis S, Deakin B, DeRubeis RJ, Dubois B, Geyer MA, Goodwin GM, Gorwood P, Jay TM, Joëls M, Mansuy IM, Meyer-Lindenberg A, Murphy D, Rolls E, Saletu B, Spedding M, Sweeney J, Whittington M, Young LJ (2012) Cognitive dysfunction in psychiatric disorders: characteristics, causes and the quest for improved therapy. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery* 11(2): 141–168. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd3628>
- Ministry of Health (2020) National Strategy for the Development of Clinical Pharmacy in Hospital Care; <https://old.mh.government.bg/bg/politiki/strategii-i-kontseptsii/strategii/> [Accessed 15.05.2025]
- Ministry of Health (2004–2012) Mental Health Policy 2004–2012 <https://www.mh.government.bg/upload/3453/politika-psihično-zdrave-2004-2012.pdf> [Accessed 25.03.2025]
- Moini J, Ross M [Eds] (2016) *Fundamentals of Pharmacology for Pharmacy Technicians*. 2016 2nd edn. CANGAGE Learning; 20 Channel Center Street, Boston, MA 02210, USA.
- Moore CH, Powell BD, Kyle JA (2018) The role of the community pharmacist in mental health. *U.S. Pharmacist* 43(11): 13–20. ISSN 01484818, Jobson Publishing Corporation.
- Morrison RL, Stomski NJ, Whately M (2018) Strategies to support medication adherence in people with serious mental illness: a literature review. *Mental Health & Prevention* 10: 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhp.2018.02.003>
- National Institute of Mental Health [NIMH] (2025) Mental Health Information. <https://www.nimh.nih.gov> [Accessed 25.01.2025]
- National Institute on Drug Abuse [NIDA] (2023) Medications for substance use disorders. <https://nida.nih.gov/> [Accessed 25.03.2025]

- NHS Guideline (2018) NHS Guidelines for the Management of QTc Prolongation in Adults Prescribed Antipsychotics. <https://www.england.nhs.uk/north/wp-content/uploads/sites/5/2018/12/QTc-flow-diagram-with-medications-final-Dec-17-A3-with-logos.pdf> [Accessed 19.08.2025]
- NHS Guideline (2020) NHS Guideline on drug-induced QT prolongation. <https://aaamedicines.org.uk/media/m13hdonk/guideline-on-drug-induced-qt-prolongation.pdf> [Accessed 19.08.2025]
- NHS Guideline (2022) NHS Guidelines for the management of serotonin syndrome. <https://rightdecisions.scot.nhs.uk/media/1831/management-of-serotonin-syndrome.pdf> [Accessed 20.08.2025]
- NHS Guideline (2025) NHS Guidelines for the Management of QTc Prolongation with Psychotropic Medication. <https://www.teww.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Psychotropic-Medication-Guidelines-for-the-Management-of-QTc-Prolongation-with-Psychotropic-Medication.pdf> [Accessed 19.08.2025]
- NHS Specialist Pharmacy Service (2023) NHS Specialist Pharmacy Service Monitoring a person during and after antidepressant switching <https://www.sps.nhs.uk/articles/monitoring-a-person-during-and-after-antidepressant-switching> [Accessed 20.08.2025]
- NHS Specialist Pharmacy Service (2024) NHS Specialist Pharmacy Service Planning and agreeing an antidepressant switching strategy. <https://www.sps.nhs.uk/articles/planning-and-agreeing-an-antidepressant-switching-strategy> [Accessed 20.08.2025]
- NICE (2014) NICE Clinical guideline for Psychosis and schizophrenia in adults: prevention and management. <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/cg178/chapter/recommendations>
- NICE (2022) Guideline. Depression in adults: treatment and management; available at: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng222/chapter/recommendations> [Accessed 21.08.2025]
- O'Reilly CL, Bell JS, Chen TF (2010) Pharmacists' beliefs about treatments and outcomes of mental disorders: a mental health literacy survey. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry* 44(12): 1089–1096. <https://doi.org/10.3109/00048674.2010.512864>
- Osterberg L, Blaschke T (2005) Adherence to Medication. *New England Journal of Medicine* 353(5):487–497. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMra050100>
- Panesar K (2016) Barriers to counseling patients with mental health disorders. *U.S. Pharmacist* 41(11): 30–33. <https://www.uspharmacist.com/article/barriers-to-counseling-patients-with-mental-health-disorders#:~:text=Health%20System-Related%20Factors%3A%20The,counseling%20and%20lack%20of%20time.&text=Other%20issues%20include%20the%20lack,of%20the%20patient%27s%20medical%20background> [Accessed 09.04.2025]
- Rickles NM, Wertheimer AI, Smith MC (2010) *Social and Behavioral Aspects of Pharmaceutical Care* (3rd edn.). Sudbury, MA: Jones & Bartlett Learning, 484 pp.
- Rieck M, Kim JA (2014) Managing drug interactions with antidepressants. *US Pharmacist* 39(11): 30–34.
- Royal Pharmaceutical Society (2018) *Mental Health Roundtable Report*.
- Rubio-Valera M, Chen TF, O'Reilly CL (2014) New roles for pharmacists in community mental health care: A narrative review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 11(10): 10967–10990. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph111010967>
- Sarris J, McIntyre E, Camfield DA (2013) Plant-based medicines for anxiety disorders, part 2: a review of clinical studies with supporting preclinical evidence. *CNS Drugs* 27(4): 301–319. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40263-013-0059-9>
- Shepherd N, Beveridge E, Parker C (2022) Impact of a pharmacist in extended role on an acute mental health ward. *Progress in Neurology and Psychiatry* 26(3): 27–30. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pnp.758>
- Soubolsky A, Halpape K (2022) The time is now for mental health care: Evaluating the impact of a clinical pharmacist on an acute mental health unit. *The Canadian Journal of Hospital Pharmacy* 75(4): 317–325. <https://doi.org/10.4212/cjhp.3210>
- Spina E, de Leon J (2007) Metabolic drug interactions with newer antipsychotics: A comparative review. *Basic & Clinical Pharmacology & Toxicology* 100(1): 4–22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1742-7843.2007.00017.x>
- Syrnyk C, Glass BD (2023) Pharmacist interventions in medication adherence in patients with mental health disorders: A scoping review. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy* 19(6): 321–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2023.05.001>
- Tai M, Vu L, Bostwick JR (2014) Antidepressant treatment concerns and recommendations for avoiding adverse events. *U.S. Pharmacist*, 39(11): 34–36. ISSN 01484818, Jobson Publishing Corporation
- The New York State Medicaid Prescriber Education Program (NYSMPEP) (2024) Metabolic Health as an Essential Consideration When Using Antipsychotic Medications. <https://nysep.nysdoh.suny.edu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Metabolic-Monitoring-of-Antipsychotic-Medications-NYSMPEP-Article-v5.2024.pdf> [Accessed 21.08.2025]
- Vandenbroucke RE, Foulon V, De Vriese C, Van Boxem T, Simoens S (2012) Evaluation of drug-drug interaction software in community and hospital pharmacy. *European Journal of Clinical Pharmacology* 68(5): 547–555.
- Wakeman SE, Barnett ML (2018) Primary care and the opioid-overdose crisis — Buprenorphine myths and realities. *New England Journal of Medicine* 379(1): 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp1802741>
- Wijesinghe R (2016) A review of pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic interactions with antipsychotics. *The Mental Health Clinician* 6(1): 21–27. <https://doi.org/10.9740/mhc.2016.01.021>
- Winstanley EL, Clark AN (2018) Engaging pharmacists to address the opioid crisis: A review of programs. *Substance Abuse* 39(2): 211–215.
- World Health Organization (1997) *The Role of the Pharmacist in the Health Care System – Preparing the Future Pharmacist: Curricular Development*. Geneva: WHO. Report No.: WHO/PHARM/97/599. https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/63817/WHO_PHARM_97_599.pdf [Accessed 01.04.2025]

Supplementary material 1

Additional information

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Data type: docx

Explanation note: **S1.** Proposal for a systematic comprehensive guide on pharmaceutical care / providing advice regarding the combined use of psychotropic medications in individuals with mental health disorders. **S2.** Framework for management (guideline for pharmaceutical care) of patients with depression. **S3.** Framework for management (guideline for pharmaceutical care) of patients with psychoactive substance addiction.

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